

THE PROXIMITY OF AN ART WITH FUNNY HANGOMS (ANECDOTES)

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Summary

The article deals with funny words (lofs) are prosaic creations built on a short plot, which by the way do not have a large volume oral. The story of the emergence of suicides, genesis has existed since humanity appeared, which had social relations.

Key words

Folklore, knowledge, plot, humanity, creation, events, assessment.

In Karakalpak folklore, funny words (lofs) are filled with detailed content, idea, a compositional structure encompassing the object. Funny words (lofs) are prosaic creations built on a short plot, which by the way do not have a large volume oral. The story of the emergence of suicides, genesis has existed since humanity appeared, which had social relations. After each person realized how he felt, knew, portrayed something good around him, he became a good critic of the events around him every day.

In most of these descriptions, without directly exposing the defects that took place in life, talking, finding flaws through laughter became vital. Over time, years, centuries, humanity develops experience, science, knowledge, revealing shortcomings on the other side, multiplication, minding, the ability to give what happened, in the style of allegory, sarcasm, grotesque. Such methods gradually began to appear both in oral and in writing.

Every nation has been told the name of famous people built in a funny sense. The simplest plots, the most interesting of which are funny algae. This is the result of the opinion expressed. With the help of these algae you have to laugh. The algae content is very rich. They can be expressed on different sides of life, human life. You cannot limit them only to negative phenomena. Positive events, funny waters have also been created.

The assessment of suicides is primarily in the find and skill of their creators. How difficult it is to find algae that can make a person laugh. Extracting these algae to the surface itself requires a lot of skill. Therefore, ridiculous algae people who can laugh, and some people cannot do it. Therefore, the revitalization of ridiculous water is a creator. Sheep farming excites algae well, serves and hears them. He hears and smiles. At the same time, they impressed and agreed with the skill of human fantasy in building a cult and laughter plot. So, gilded algae are human semantic feed.

Khuja Nasriddin, thanks to his dedication, overcomes arrogant, weak people in society. All this time he careful the people, was surrounded by people who suffered from someone. The people of Nasriddin, not spending their energy on enemies, on those who suppressed the people were laughter nonsense. He left heavy situations with skill. The funny hangoms of Khuja Nasriddin from oral among the people – to oral with great interest in his father. Aldar kusa is a slave and lofist of the Kazakh people. He was all the time with his compatriot,

rejoiced in joy and fed the people with his interesting hangs. Aldar is easily kept from people. To overcome the Aldar desert of Kazakhstan, two people came, named Dukhtar and Mukhtar, invite him for a walk and prepare one cauldron. The two Aldar sleeps about who laughed well at the finger to bury him. When they actually sleep, Aldar pretends to run away.

They woke up singing dreams to each other. Dukhtar, riding a horse, says Mukhtar got on a white horse. After hearing that, Aldar said I waited a little while for you. If you look at Kazan then Fig. Both deceive Aldar and disintegrate. Here we see how Aldar knew how is clever. He lived in the second half of the 19th century and died at the age of 70-75, was buried in the Tayshak cemetery on the shores of Lake Yesimuzak in the Karauzak district. The nickname Umirbek is "like," this refers to people who know how to laugh, know how to laugh joke.

A man who lived in history and lived in Chimbay. The famous dancer Merep is a contemporary of the tentek. The glory of his era went into the world, and at the competition in artistic wrestling, a man appeared before him who could not be a person.

Among the Karakalpaks, all talking funny algae under the name Umirbek. Each smile of Umirbek symbolizes a huge mysterious manner. A characteristic sign of Umirbek's anecdotes is that ironic thought was always known at the end of the conversation. In his proverbs, the factual are the flaws that occur in everyday life in each person, and sometimes in a group of people. We see that at some point person was built on weaknesses that cannot be sensitive, and when felt, they cannot be so reliable. But these are the things that need to be worked out. For example: Umirbek one day eats horse. He hurries again, not knowing the horse. "Take all your horses, I'll shoot my horse." People who hears this find a suicide horse, and a horse in appearance. He knew it was his horse and owned his horse. We admit we found Umirbeck's horse with huge flesh in it. Umirbek's have become a good textbook for people. In the latifs of Umirbek there are various events in life, various people in everyday life, Umirbek's communication with him, his superstitious actions, statements that he is guilty of slavery.

There is a huge logic, philosophy, thoughts, feelings in gilded algae. Thoughts that cover everything that is characteristic of the fate of a person visible in everyday life are conveyed in a manner, hung and smiled. The humorous pressure on gilded algae is puzzling for people who lived during this time.

In Karakalpaks from the 70-80s of the XX century became a cultural accent, especially among intellectuals, scientists. Then scientists and journalists took their place and any professional who came from hand released and distributed the latifs. In the current situation, talented people intervened in this level. The famous slaves of that time, the owners of talents that can turn latifs into algae, as well as extract funny algae from them form a power in our people.

The most famous of them are K. Ayimbetov, G. Ubaydullayev, S. Kamalov, J. Bekmuratov. There were people whose names are widely known to leaders and people of different professions. The public basics in which they worked, as well as the places where they were in the workplace, became the most interesting type of funny algae. They themselves issued latifs and talked about how they built slaves created by others. The above people are masters and distributors of slavery. These latifs created by great men are finally doomed.

He pays special attention to various events in the life of diving slaves, people with different abilities in life, open treatment by Latvians, what they did not hesitate to learn, the

power of artistic self-esteem, and most importantly, funny volatile waters. Latiphaeans do not share a group, category, large-small state of people.

As in the case of the "joke with the father," if someone feels that you are gone or something recognizable, then laughs at him in some form. They can be created either in the literal sense or in the magical indirect sense. Therefore, you always smile at their ridiculous algae. The fact is that it is built on a short plot, and it hits hard. Because there is a living fact under it.

Therefore, everyone likes it, everyone is interesting, everyone laughs. Even if the owner of an erroneous profession hears it, she may not laugh at it. Because gilded algae was built only on the facts that are, and may be. Therefore, hearing him, he enjoys and rejoices. The Karakalpak people are a people rich in algae since ancient times. Despite the fact that our ancestors overcame all heavy parts of time, not a single day aroused people's feelings, traditions, interdisciplinary dialogue. He named the place of both folk festivities and ceremonies, found appropriate artistic ties for them, said that if they spoke, they would it.

The weekly newspaper "Argument i Fakti", published in Moscow, the most widespread in the world, gives quarterly leaflets. At the end of the year, they produce all called "latifs". Their authors are ordinary people from all over Russia. For example, in one of the issues of the newspaper, the author V. Sumin wrote: "Aphorism is a short and accurate skirt. There is a lot of talent in the karakalpaks. Despite the fact that they worked on different fronts of life, they even gave life to people, the future, unity, well-being, independence. I said he had a weapon.

In the difficulties experienced by the Karakalpaks, there was no people who would hide their opinions. Even if Callacy leaves, truth does not displace language. He survived the fate of the people, having survived poor suffering, slavery, particles, quarrels, fights. As for language in any scandal, the karakalpaks were able to defend their will. For a century, folk talents served: bakhshi, fats, kissakhans, amateurs, Chechens, masters of sports, not a single bride, in collaboration with the people of the country. They developed traditions at the level.

A person does not in the head - he used folk traditions worthy of all this. All of them were dressed in art form. He solved questions about what sweet language is. There are various ways to soften language. One of them is folklore, forever present from ancestors - a people's sage. It's endless. Our folklore is only an artistic golden treasure created by ancestors.

In Karakalpak life, in wide sections of people, there is not a single natural talent who has walking, what he said, what he did, has humor what he can do without doing it himself. God gave them this paralysis -beat. However, in the nature of these people, I do not try to stay like this.

This is a talent who killed himself. Created in this way. It is necessary to educate them. Whoever they communicated with, entered into a dialogue addressed they would spend these good qualities. The humor satire in which their actions take place. It doesn't work deep. And on natural water, and at work, everything is ridiculous.

These swords are not negative, but, on the contrary, positive. He is also respected by those around him. Because their behavior is good for everyone. Interesting conversation, interesting answer, interesting move. These are artists, they play in roles, mocking or not. Such people are smart, benevolent, most of all know how to behave, become active, white

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